

A Proposed Retrofit for Bridges Subjected to Wave Forces

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Abstract

Damage due to recent hurricanes along the Gulf Coast of Mexico publicized the need for research of engineering practices in coastal areas. Specifically, many bridges near the coast were not designed for storm surge and wind induced wave loads. Many of these damaged bridges are being rebuilt higher with correspondingly higher costs. The following proposal concerns using existing seismic retrofitting techniques for simply supported bridges as a solution to this problem. The proposed connection design provides suggestions for retrofitting existing structures and guidance for designers on future construction.

Background

Recent hurricanes along the Gulf Coast of Mexico, such as Ivan in 2004 and Katrina in 2005, completely damaged a number of coastal bridges. See Figure 1: Damaged Bridges Relative to Storm Surge in Louisiana . The combination of storm surge and wind induced waves caused significant lateral and uplift loads. Figure 2: Unseating of Spans shows that these loads were able to completely displace some bridge spans. Figure 3: Bridge Deck Subject to Surge and Waves During Storm Conditions shows the problem of lateral and uplift loads on the bridge deck. This article considers the case of the I-10 Twin Span bridges (Twin Span) over Lake Pontchartrain which was damaged by Hurricane Katrina. The original Twin Span crossed Lake Pontchartrain near the east coast of the lake. The east-bound span led to Slidell, LA, while the west-bound span led to New Orleans, LA. See Figure 4: Typical SS Bridge Section (NTS) for a typical cross-section of this bridge. The Twin Span was 8.69 km (5.4 mi) long and was a low height series of 433 simply supported spans each 19.8 m (65 ft) long (Okeil and Cai). The spans were precast prestressed concrete (PPC) girders that rested on cast-in-place pile caps and risers to account for roadway slopes. The piles were either single or double row 1372 mm (54 in) circular PPC. Storm surge, wind induced waves, and potential entrapped air forces unseated many of the spans from the risers.

A new Twin Span is under construction parallel to the original bridges. The new bridges will be 30 feet higher than the average water elevation of Lake Pontchartrain and are designed to be above the storm surge elevation of a hurricane event. The bridge decks should not, theoretically, see storm surge or wind induced wave loads. This project has a preliminary total cost of \$800 million and schedule of five years (Twin Span Bridge).

Other designs should be considered to provide guidance for future construction and suggestions for retrofitting existing structures that are cost effective. Okeil and Cai (2008) suggested several theoretical methods of reducing the loading. Open railing systems and venting holes on the bridge deck may relieve hydrostatic pressure. The entrapped air and water would then have a channel to escape, thus reducing the probability of uplift. Simply supported bridges may not provide continuity and be susceptible to uplift while rigid joints may transfer too much force and damage the substructure. Existing seismic or offshore techniques may be

adapted for this problem of wave forces on bridge decks. Flexible joints, for example, provide continuity while limiting damage to the substructure and should be investigated. This article will explore this one example of a flexible joint retrofit.

Research in this field has only become a topic of concern recently, and, consequently, limited literature exists. See Douglass et al. (2006) for a comprehensive review of studies on this subject. Most notably, Edge et al. (2008) completed applicable empirical research. This work consisted of experiments at the Haynes Coastal Engineering Laboratory at Texas A & M University on scaled bridge models with a similar design as the Twin Span. Two physical models were tested at a 1:20 scale, a flat plate model and a girder span model. The models were applied with combinations of surge and waves, and parameters such as water depth and wave period, height, and type served as variables for the experiments. Force transducers and strain gauges measured the models' performance under these wave loadings. The study concluded that existing methods of predicting loads are not accurate and should not be used for design. Based on the empirical model, Edge et al. (2006) proposed a method to estimate the hydrostatic lateral and uplift loads for coastal bridges.

Research Opportunities

The objective of this article is to introduce the idea of using existing seismic retrofitting techniques for simply supported bridges as a solution to this problem of storm surge and wind induced wave loads. The Federal Highway Administration report, Seismic Retrofitting Manual for Highway Structures: Part 1 – Bridges, provides detailed measures to seismically retrofit bridges. One way to stiffen the connection between the superstructure and substructure is through joint restrainers. The joint restrainers are designed to limit the relative displacement at the expansion joints when the original joint design does not prevent loss of support. Joint restrainers should be designed within the elastic range and symmetric restrainers should be used at each joint to prevent eccentric movement. While pounding may still occur at the joint, the restrainers prevent unseating of the span and total damage of the structure. The restrainers may be either cables or bars. Cables are most commonly used as joint restrainers due to the economic advantage and the increased flexibility that accommodates both transverse and vertical movements.

The most commonly used cable is a galvanized 19 mm (0.75 in) diameter steel cable. The end connections are galvanized, cold-swaged fittings and 25 mm (1 in) diameter ASTM A-449 threaded studs. For load and resistance factor design, the cables are assumed to have a tensile capacity of 174 kN (39.1 kips). The cables are typically pre-tensioned, which results in a modulus of elasticity in the range of 69,000 MPa (10,000 ksi) to 124,000 MPa (18,000 ksi). See Figure 5: Typical Restrainer Anchorage Detail for required clearances and dimensions.

For the joint retrofit, drilling or coring of the existing concrete structure is required. Careful consideration should be given to the specified clearances as outlined in the Seismic Retrofitting Manual for Highway Structures. Additionally, care should be taken not to cut existing reinforcing steel, prestressing tendons, etc. by obtaining "as built" plans of the structure. Seismic Retrofitting Manual for Highway Structures also presents guidance on the

design of anchorage and additional connection issues. The manual recommends when possible to use drilling because there is less potential for damage of the reinforcing or prestressing steel.

Closure of the joint will transfer force from one span to an adjacent span. Therefore, the restrainers must be designed to resist the inertia forces of both adjacent spans and must include an appropriate factor of safety. For a conservative design, the design force is the weight of the adjacent spans. Future research should outline a less conservative approach to calculate the design forces.

This suggested retrofit may only be used if the substructure is able to resist the forces transferred by the restrainers. Restrainers alone may not be sufficient and often should be used in addition to other retrofits such as seat extensions, bearing strengthening, and bearing replacement. Often the failure mechanism of these restrainer assemblies is punching shear. To prevent punching shear failure often the diaphragms should be strengthened with concrete bolsters. It should be noted that these devices do not dissipate significant amounts of energy because they are designed to remain elastic. Additional research about other potential energy dissipating devices may be required.

The question of course is whether or not these seismic retrofitting techniques work for the unique loading seen during a hurricane event. A possible method to test this hypothesis is to conduct experiments similar to Edge in which a scaled retrofitted bridge model is subjected to simulated wave forces. The response of the structure may then be measured. This procedure would help develop functional relationships between the variables and identify important dimensionless parameters.

A force function may be developed by assuming a wave theory and using least square procedures to develop the force function coefficients from the measured wave profile. Based on the description and the response of the scaled retrofitted bridge model, existing analytical or numerical procedures may be used to derive the equation of motion for the structure. The outcome of this experiment would be knowledge of the effect of these retrofit procedures on the response of the structure. Recommended analysis procedures may also provide guidance for engineers on future construction.

Conclusion

Bridges along the Gulf Coast of Mexico were not designed adequately for the loads caused by a hurricane event. Typically, load calculations for bridge designs in these coastal areas emphasized gravity, lateral, and impulse loads, but little investigation existed concerning the response caused by storm surge and wind induced wave loads. Recent studies have determined prediction models for the lateral and uplift forces on bridge decks during a hurricane event, however, research has not been conducted on how to mitigate these forces. The suggestions in this article may be a method to prevent significant damage to these structures, but research is needed on the subject. The incentive for future research is the cost and time savings as compared to building bridges higher.

References

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Figure 1: Damaged Bridges Relative to Storm Surge in Louisiana (Padgett, DesRoches and Nielson)

Figure 2: Unseating of Spans (Padgett, DesRoches and Nielson)

Figure 3: Bridge Deck Subject to Surge and Waves During Storm Conditions (Douglass, Chen and Olsen)

Figure 4: Typical SS Bridge Section (NTS)

Figure 5: Typical Restrainer Anchorage Detail (Buckle, Friedland and Mander)